

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-178-ADH-10% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	46	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	4 278
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/10/2023 10:57:12 CST		
Date Processed:	6/22/2023 22:32:22 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.658	7430743	50.32	498234
2	11.225	7337006	49.68	381010

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-278-ADH-10% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	79	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 278
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/10/2023 3:40:45 PM CST		
Date Processed:	6/22/2023 10:44:01 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.082	495762	4.99	29643
2	11.735	9446451	95.01	463600